

Modeling Magnetic Basement in Relationship to Hydrocarbon Habitats in the Central Niger Delta, Nigeria

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all the authors. Author DAO designed the study, performed the modeling and wrote the first draft. Author AJI performed the data reduction and analysis. Author SEL purchased the data, analyzed the data using filtering methods. Author EZ analyzed the data using modeling methods and final proof reading. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Aeromagnetics has over the years been used as a reconnaissance tool for hydrocarbon exploration. Modeling of source of magnetic anomalies can also reveal basin depth and configuration of supposed hydrocarbon habitats. This study was done using (8) aeromagnetic maps on a scale of 1:100,000 covering the central Niger Delta states in Nigeria. The data was digitized and processed using the United States Geological Survey potential field software's version 2.2 for map merging, reduction to pole, polynomial filtering, horizontal gradient magnitude (HGM), Wenner deconvolution, forward and inverse modeling (pdep and saki programs). The result indicates areas around Benin River, Warri, Kwale and Aboh with more dominant shallow depths (0.8 km-2.01 km) with minor areas reaching deeper sources (2.5 km-4.5 km) while areas around Forcados, Burutu and Ahoada have predominantly deeper sources (2.5 km-4.5 km). Generally, there is an agreement

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in all the depth-derived sources of an increase in sediment thickness accumulation from the onshore (Warri areas) towards the offshore (Burutu) with horst and graben structures as indicated from the saki models. The identified grabens are the recognized possible hydrocarbon habitat, which forms potential targets for hydrocarbon exploration prior to seismic exploration.

Keywords: Hdrocarbon; modeling; habitats; polynomial filtering; Wenner deconvolution; horst; graben.

1. INTRODUCTION

Modeling aeromagnetic data has been widely used as a reconnaissance tool for hydrocarbon exploration. Its ability to locate depth to magnetic sources vis-a-vis sediment thickness, collect data over a wide area in inaccessible areas within a short time and its low cost makes it a useful geophysical mapping tool [1,2].

The Niger Delta clastic wedge is formed after a failed arm of a triple junction (aulacogen) that originally developed during the break up of South America and African plates in Jurassic period (Burke, 1972; Whiteman, 1982). The Niger Delta clastic wedge prograded by subsidence aided by the chain and charcot oceanic transform faults [3]. Gravity potential aided further subsidence driven by shelf and upper shelf slope deposition of sediments [4,5].

The study area lies within latitude 3°.00'-6°.00' N and longitude 5°.00'-7°.00' E which includes Edo, Ondo, Delta, Bayelsa, Rivers, Imo and Anambra states in Nigeria (Fig. 1).

So far, aeromagnetic studies have been done by studying magnetic profiles on regional data sets and some parts of offshore Niger Delta [6,7,8]. The onshore Nigeria Delta has not been modeled in details using magnetics to unravel the deep-seated hydrocarbon habitats. This study will reveal the structured configuration of the basement and will serve as an aid in controlling further seismic exploration targets.

2. GEOLOGY OF THE STUDY AREA

The Niger Delta forms one of the world's major hydrocarbon provinces with Tertiary sedimentary fill reaching a maximum thickness of about 12 km [9]. The area has three major formations. These are the Akata, Agbada, and Benin formations. Generally, only the Benin Formation (continental sandstones) is expressed from the geological map [10]. The topmost unit is the recent alluvium underlain by Holocene mudstones, sandstones and gravels. These overlie the Pleistocene Benin sands covering about 70% of the study area. This unit is underlain by Oligocene-Miocene Ogwashi-Asaba Formation consisting of clays,

Fig. 1. Location map of the study area with well B indicating position of an existing drilled oil well (Digitized from geologic map of Nigeria, NGS 2010)

Fig. 2. Geological map of the study area (Digitized from geologic map of Nigeria, NGS2010)

sands and seams of lignite. This unit is also underlain by the Lower Eocene Ameki Group which constitute the oldest rocks within the study area and consists of green sandy clay and white clayey sandstones [11]. This unit covers only about 5% of the study area (Fig. 2 above).

3. DATA ANALYSIS

Eight sheets of half by half ($0.5^0 \times 0.5^0$) degree aeromagnetic total intensity field maps on a scale of 1:100,000 were acquired from the Nigerian Geological Survey Agency Kaduna. A suite of United States potential field software version 2.2, surfer 9.0 software and the Geological map of Nigeria (1994) were used for this study. The aeromagnetic maps were digitized at 1.0 km interval to avoid the problem of frequency aliasing. The digitized data set was in xyz format. The combined digitalized values for the maps was 11,200 data points which was processed and used by the following software batch programs: A2XYZ, DETOUR, P2GRD, PC-CONTOUR, PLUGGRID, ADDGRD, PREP5, DE-PREP5, CK_DIMS, JMEGER, SURFIT, FFTFIL, PREP5, DE-PREP5, PDEPT, HDEP, F_RTP, SAKI and SURFER 9.0. For a detailed understanding of the application of these software programs, the interested reader should refer to United States Geological Survey potential field software version 2.0 (Phillips 1997).

Since all the aeromagnetic sheets were flown at the same level of 500 m above sea level, no

continuation was applied. All the data were merged using ADDGRD and JMERGER software to produce the total magnetic field intensity map of the study area. Also, the merged digitized processed file for the entire data set was used in SURFER 9.0 software to produce the colored total field intensity map. The merged grid file produced from P2GRD software was used by in the following software PLUGGRID, PREP5, FFTFIL, F_RTP and DE-PREP5 to produce the reduction to pole map [12,2,13,14,15,16] and shown in Figs. 3a, 3b, and 4.

The reduction to the pole grid file was applied to the SURFIT software in generating regional and residual separations. The filtered residual grid file was used to produce the residual anomaly map of the study area shown in Fig. 5.

The residual grid file was used on the PROFILE-X software to extract magnetic profile lines perpendicular to the trends of the residual anomalies. A total of 6 profiles were generated as profiles which were further used by the P-DEPTH software to generate the forward model files. During this process, the Wenner deconvolution option of analysis was used and the depths plots generated during the forward modeling process as shown in Figs. 6a to 6f.

Also, the horizontal gradient magnitude depth analysis was performed using the HDEP software to generate the horizontal gradient magnitude (HGM) [12,13,14] and shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 3a. Merged total magnetic field intensity map of the study area (After removing 25,000 gammas and contoured at 10nT interval)

Fig. 3b. Coloured total magnetic field intensity of the study area (contoured at 10nT interval)

Fig. 4. Reduced to pole total magnetic field intensity map of the study area (contoured at 10nT interval)

Fig. 5. Residual polynomial magnetic field intensity map of the study area (contoured at 10nT interval)

Fig. 6a. Forward model showing Wenner depth basements contacts along Ahoda profile line

Fig. 6b. Forward model showing Wennerdepth basements contacts along Aboh profile line

Fig. 6c. Forward model showing Wenner depth basements contacts along Burutu profile line

Fig. 6d. Forward model showing Wennerdepth basements contacts along Forcados profile line

Fig. 6e. Forward model showing Wennerdepth basements contacts along Patani profile line

Fig. 6f. Forward model showing Wenner depth basements contacts along Warri profile line

Both Horizontal gradient magnitude and Wenner deconvolution depths were considered during modeling, which involves the placement of bodies, susceptibilities of bodies, total field intensities, declinations, inclination, and profile lines azimuths were all used as parameters to generate the forward modeled file [17]. The

forward modeled file was then used in the inverse modeling saki software as an input file and, with the same modeling parameters above, mathematical iterations was employed to generate the inverse modeled plots shown in Figs. 8a-8g.

Fig. 7. Depth horizontal gradient magnitude map of the study area

Fig. 8a. Forward and inverse model interpretation of residual magnetic anomalies along Ahoada profile

Legend: 1, Sedimentary rocks ,
2,3, intrusives
4, 5, 6, 7, 8 , basement rocks

Fig. 8b. Forward and inverse model interpretation of residual magnetic anomalies along Aboh profile

*Legend: 1, Sedimentary rocks,
2,3, intrusives
4,5,6,7, basement rocks*

Fig. 8c. Forward and inverse model interpretation of residual magnetic anomalies along Burutu profile line

*Legend: 1, Sedimentary rocks,
2,3, intrusives
4,5,6,7, basement rocks*

Fig. 8d. Forward and inverse model interpretation of residual magnetic anomalies along Burutu profile line

*Legend: 1, Sedimentary rocks,
2,3, intrusives
4,5,6,7, basement rocks*

Fig. 8e. Forward and inverse model interpretation of residual magnetic anomalies along Forcados profile2 line
 Legend: 1, Sedimentary rocks ,
 2,3, intrusives
 4,5,6,7,8 , basement rocks

Fig. 8f. Forward and inverse model interpretation of residual magnetic anomalies along Patani profile line
 Legend: 1, Sedimentary rocks,
 2,3, intrusives
 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 , basement rocks

Fig. 8g. Forward and inverse model interpretation of residual magnetic anomalies along Warri profile line
 Legend: 1, Sedimentary rocks,
 2,3, intrusives
 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 , basement rocks

Table 1. Comparative depths derived from Wenner deconvolution, horizontal gradient magnitude and forward and inverse modelling (Saki)

S/N	Town aeromagnetic sheet	Forward and inverse Saki model depths (Km)	Horizontal gradient magnitude depths (km)	Wenner deconvolution depths (km)
1	Benin River	-	1.0-4.0	-
2	WARRI	1.5-3.2	2.0-4.0	1.0-4.0
3	KWALE	-	1.0-3.0	-
4	ABOH	0.8-1.8	1.0-4.0	1.0-5.0
5	FORCADOS	2.5-3.4	4.5-12.00	3.0-4.5
6	BURUTU	0.98-4.0	1.0-4.0	2.0-4.5
7	PATANI	1.0-2.3	1.0-4.0	2.0-3.0
8	AHOADA	1.0-3.0	2.0-6.0	2.0-4.5

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This study searches areas with sufficient thickness of sedimentary rock sequences that may act as hydrocarbon habitats [18,10,9]. The modelled Wenner profiles (Figs. 6a-f) indicate the contact plots of surface line between the sediment thickness and the source (bodies) which reveals a configuration pattern of horst and graben structures. The plots indicate shallow magnetic basements between 0.8 km and 1.5 km, and deeper sources between 2.0 km and 4.5 km. Also, the horizontal gradient magnitude depth map (Fig. 7) has shallow sources depths between 1.0 km and 3.0 km and deeper sources between 4.0 km-12.0 km. Similar works have been done by different authors [19,12,14,16]. There is a general increment in thickness of sediments from Benin River, Warri, Kwale and Aboh towards areas around Forcados, Burutu, Ahoada and Patani. Forward and inverse modeling was done using Saki software, which utilized controlled depth estimates from Wenner deconvolution and horizontal gradient magnitude. The Saki model plots (Figs. 8a-f) indicate that the Forcados area has the highest sedimentary thickness of 3.4 km. Other shallow sources range between 0.8 km and 2.3 km.

Generally, the subsurface structural configuration is that of a horst representing the shallow depths, and grabens the deeper sedimentary layers. As shown in Table 1 above, a comparative analysis of the depth to magnetic sources derived from Wenner deconvolution, Horizontal Gradient Magnitude (HGM) and forward and inverse Saki modeling shows a good correlation in the results obtained from the different methods.

5. CONCLUSION

Modeling of aeromagnetic total field intensity was done with the aim of identifying possible

hydrocarbon habitat. Different methods were used to assist in the placement of magnetic source bodies during forward and inverse modeling. The results evidenced deep and shallow-depth magnetic anomalies which indicate horst and graben structures. The deep graben areas may form better hydrocarbon habitats around Forcados and Burutu, which are identified as prominent seismic exploration targets for further hydrocarbon investigations.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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